

“TOURISM” TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES, THEIR STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES

Farokhat Yunusova

Uzbekistan State World Languages university, 2nd year master student on the branch of Linguistics.

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Introduction

Today, along with other areas of linguistics, the field of terminology plays an important role in the development of linguistics. The number of theoretical and practical terms in this area is growing from year to year. At the same time, today's scholars are conducting an in-depth analysis of the specific features of scientific text materials in different languages, methods of structure and formation of terms, terminology standards and sorting issues. This article mainly focuses on terms related to tourism, their structure and meanings and compares them in two different languages English and Uzbek. Coordinating the similarities and differences of systems in two or more languages allows us to lay the groundwork for a comparative typological study of terms, both in the field of lexical semantics and in the field of systematic self-management. There is no unity in the goals, principles, and methodology of research in this area of research, as they are primarily focused on solving specific problems of comparable terminology. Currently, the field of tourism is also developing rapidly, and the education system has begun to train specialists in new areas of tourism. All this requires the development of an accelerated terminology system in the field of tourism. From the above considerations, it can be seen that the system of terms "tourism" is the basis for the media, and its study is the most important condition for successful professional activity and the organization of tourism.

There is no dictionary of specific terms in the field of tourism in Uzbek. This makes it difficult for those involved in this activity. In addition, foreign tourists do not understand the terms of the Uzbek people in this area. It is no exaggeration to say that this is causing the tourism business to slow down a bit.

“Terminology, the discipline concerned with the study and compilation of specialized terms is not a new field of study, but only in recent decades has it been systematically developed, with full consideration of its principles, bases and methodology. Its social and political importance has now also been recognized on both the national and the international scale.”¹

¹ Cabré, M. Teresa. “Terminology: theory, methods and applications”. - John Benjamins Publishing Co. Amsterdam, Netherlands. 1999. P. 1

Following Auger (1988) we identify four basic periods in the development of modern terminology:

- a. The origins (1930 – 1960)- characterized by the design of methods for the systematic formation of terms. The first theoretical texts by Wüster and Lotte appeared at this time. ²
- b. The structuring of the field (1960 – 1975)- first databanks appeared, and the international coordination of principles of terminology processing was initiated. During this period the first approaches were made to standardize terminology within a language.
- c. The boom (1975 – 1985)- marked by the proliferation of language planning and terminology projects; some countries like Israel, had begun their language policies earlier.
- d. The expansion (1985 – present³)- International cooperation is broadened and consolidated, an international networks are created to link agencies and countries which share characteristics or are interested in cooperation. Examples of this are the exchange of information and the international cooperation in training terminologists.

Materials and methods

Terminology is deeply rooted in applications, such as specialized dictionary compilation, specialized translation, document indexing and/or classification, knowledge modeling, language planning and standardization. This means that terminology (its theoretical and methodological principles) aims first and foremost to provide answers to the questions raised by these applications.

Due to the development of methodology in the recent decades, there are many methods available to use while doing linguistic research. So that componential-analysis method, comparative analysis method, distributional method, lingual-cultural analysis , deductive method have been used on this.

According to our analysis of the scientific literature on tourism (Makarenko⁴, Zorin ⁵), it is possible to distinguish four stages in the history of English tourism, which correspond to the stages of formation of English terminology. At the heart of the division into these periods are the feasibility and social bases and

² Wüster, Eugen. 1968. *The Machine Tool: An Interlingual Dictionary of Basic Concepts*. London: Technical Press.

³ Auger, Pierre. 1988. “La terminologie au Quebec et dans le monde, de la naissance à la maturité”. *Actes du sixième colloque OLF-STQ de terminologie. L’ère nouvelle de la terminologie*, 27–59. Quebec: Gouvernement du Québec.

⁴ Макаренко С.Н., Саак А.Э. *История туризма*. — Таганрог: Издательство ТРТУ, 2003. С. 94

⁵ Зорин И.В., Каверина Т.П., Квартальнов В.А. и др. *Менеджмент туризма. Туризм как вид деятельности: Учебник*. М.: Финансы и статистика, 2006. С. 406

conditions, as well as the targeted functions of tourism at different stages of development.

The first stage - *the "prototype of tourist activity"* - covers the period from antiquity to the end of the XIX century, during which the main reasons for the British to travel were trade, medicine, education.

The second stage - *"the beginning of the development of mass tourism"* - covers the entire XIX century, and at this stage began to emerge methods of tourism management, material and technical base, and, of course, further improved the system of terms.

The third stage - *"mass conveyor tourism"* - coincided with the beginning of the XX century and lasted until the end of World War II. "The development of tourism at this stage is characterized by the fact that the services provided are not demanding, and their package is standard.

The fourth stage - *"mass differentiated tourism"* - began after World War II and continues to this day. This stage of tourism development implies a variety of needs and motivations of tourists, the presence of a large number of narrow specialized segments in the structure of tourist demand, the diversity of services offered.

Tourism terminology in the Uzbek language is in its infancy and as a result of development in tourism field its composition is being enriched by other special units. It is natural that the more percent of touristic terms in Uzbek are English words if we consider the facts that the birthplace of tourism was England and the leading status of English terms in international terminology.

"Language and society are inextricably linked and take place in society all changes are reflected in its language. It has entered the life of society new concepts, events from the linguocultural conceptosphere of society in addition to their own language resources to take place in other languages and words are mastered." ⁶ This, in turn, ensures enriching of dictionary of language layer with new lexical (-phraseological) units and it looks to sustainable development in the linguocultural environment.

According to R. Jomonov, "The most important (extra-linguistic) factors in word acquisition are "political, economic relations between nations and cultural ties; scientific development; media activities expansion; increasing demand for translated literature; advertising and texts in visual aids; increasing demand for foreign languages and so on. ⁷"

⁶ Sirojiddinov Sh. On the factors of word acquisition // Uzbek language and literature, 2017. - № 4. - P.83.

⁷ Jomonov R.O. Problems of word acquisition and spelling in Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2013. - P.38

Results

The followings can be noted as the main sources of the linguistic factors in the development of Uzbek tourist terms

1. Specialization of the meaning of common words or term formation using words and morphemes in the native language
For example: mehmonxona, nomer, transport, mavsum, yotoqxona, shahar tomoshasi, sayyoh, diniy-ziyorat, maqbara, obida,
2. Creation of alternatives of the accepted terms in the native language. Price list- narxlar varaqasi, leaflets, booklets, catalogs can be a good example.

Common words are something in the field of science and technology or as a name of the concept can have a characteristic feature of the term. For example, recreational zone (recreation area).

It should be taken into consideration that there are several groups of potential users and when it comes to using and designing modern terminological dictionaries each one of them require to have a complex set with different levels. According to Rossenbeck⁸, modern market economy should include multifunctional feature in it which means while compiling tourism dictionaries we should consider users which group to belong. One of the most famous recent linguists, Isabel Balteiro, suggests following consumer groups of specialized vocabularies and we provide examples in the tourism industry:

- Specialists: developers of tourism statistics, i.e. experts involved in the implementation, editing and monitoring of tourism conditions, developers of tourism services and products.
- Semi-professionals : people who use a part of these terms often, especially due to their profession - tour operators, travel agents and guides; tourism promotion representatives.
- Students: potential tourists and people who are studying at special universities or related directions for instance, tourism, macroeconomics, marketing or management
- Intermediaries: intermediate group members who uses these words sometimes for a particular reason such as translators, journalists and writers.

⁸ Rossenbeck, Klaus (2005). 'Die zweisprachige Fachlexikographie in the new and nearest Wörterbuchforschung; Lexicographica 21, p. 18.

In modern English language touristic terms were formed with the help following ways of word-building:

- Affixation. Affixation is a process which involves adding bound morphemes to roots which results in a newly-created derivative. Whereas we can distinguish many types of this process, the English language generally makes use of two — prefixation and suffixation. Ex: charter, bumping.
- Word composition. Word composition is creating compound words by joining two or more stems. Compound words, in contrast to word combination, are structurally, semantically, phonetically and graphically whole units. Example : baby-sitting service, bungee jumping, transit hotel
- Abbreviation. In English tourism terminology abbreviations are also found; for example; “ISO” – International Organization for Standardization – world-wide federation founded 1947
- Conversion. In modern word building process on tourism terminology, semantic derivation can observed too. For instance. “twin” – “used with such nouns as beds (two single beds) and room (a room with two such from noun “twin” – “either of the two children born together of the same mother”;
- Word borrowings. Taking new words from other languages to the base of English touristic terminology can be considered to less common way of word formation.

Structural description of touristic terminological groups in Uzbek

In the 30s of XX century many Uzbek terminological dictionaries were compiled and published. At the same point, theoretical issues about history of terms, the meaning and subject of the terms groups grammatical structure and formation of terms, way of development and source of enrichment. Though terminological system has not yet been studied theoretically, tourism terminology has a special place in Uzbek terminology. Structurally, simple, complex and composite terms might be observed in Uzbek. According to genetic feature, simple terms divided into two groups:

- Simple pre-existing touristic terms in Uzbek;
- Simple touristic terms which is directed borrowed from international languages.

1. Terms that are actively used in the field tourism which was created based on the internal capabilities of Uzbek, like bayram, bojxona, buyurtma,

mablag`, marosim, mijoz, mozor, mehmonxona, qala, qo`riqxon, qabulxon, mehmonxona, safar.

2. The most effective method of borrowing words in modern stage of language development is calque. It is the way of conveyance the conception with existent units which is non-existent in a language. When the problem of word acquisition analyzed it is found that direct word acquisition from other languages is active in Uzbek. Ex: apartment, marketing, manager, transfer.

Discussion

The theoretical value is of the comparative typological study of the terminological systems of the English and Uzbek languages represent the theoretical significance of this scientific work. A comparative study of the system of terms makes it possible to identify a number of typological features of the languages being analyzed, which in turn reveal the peculiarities of the lexemes of tourist terminology. The practical value - lexicology, lexicography, ideography, comparative linguistics and comparative typology can serve as a material for the preparation of lecture texts for higher education students and students majoring in tourism. It can also be used to create bilingual or trilingual dictionaries.

The use of the language makes possible to find the strong relationship between word and its meaning, deepening of existing scientific knowledge, formation of new paradigms and finding new words to express the phenomena. For that reason there can be found synonymy of terms in Uzbek language as well as there are some doublets. like: otel – mehmonxona, nomer – xona, marshrut – yo`nalish, reception, adminstratsiya – ma`muriyat , turist – sayyoh , turizm – sayohat , agentlik – tashkilot.

Conclusion

Considering the theoretical difficulties associated with the definition of what is terminology and the general conditions for the existence of technical terms, the conclusion might be drawn that this subject should best be left in the hands of the subject experts of each field of knowledge who have to resolve problems of naming and systematic classification, or alternatively that is should become the responsibility of language planners and organizations charged with standardization or other regulation of language. However, since it is largely for sociolinguistic reasons that a specific autonomous activity of terminology has come into being, it appears necessary to explore the history of this activity and

the various areas of knowledge that contribute to the constitution of what is now increasingly being considered an independent discipline.

The results of the study show that both English and Uzbek terminology of international tourism in general is characterized by a surplus of means of formal expression of concepts, that is, these terminologies tend to be synonymous. Quantitative analysis shows that the level of synonymy in English tourist terminology is high. Synonymy of terms is considered to be one of the types of concepts of terms and incompatibility of terms, it is noted that there is an excess of means of formal expression of the concept. The problem of synonymy of terms, the use of several special lexical units to name a concept, remains one of the main and most important problems of terminology.

References

1. Auger, Pierre. 1988. "La terminologie au Quebec et dans le monde, de la naissance à la maturité". Actes du sixième colloque OLF-STQ de terminologie. L'ère nouvelle de la terminologie, 27–59. Quebec: Gouvernement du Québec.
2. Cabré, M. Teresa. "Terminology: theory, methods and applications". - John Benjamins Publishing Co. Amsterdam, Netherlands. 1999. P. 1
3. Cultural information in translation dictionaries Shirinova R.H. Scientific News Philology 2017, No. p. 2.
4. Jomonov R.O. Problems of word acquisition and spelling in Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2013. - P.38
5. Rossenbeck, Klaus (2005). 'Die zweisprachige Fachlexikographie in the new and nearest Worterbuchforschung; Lexicographica 21, p. 18.
6. Sirojiddinov Sh. On the factors of word acquisition // Uzbek language and literature, 2017. - № 4. - P.83.
7. Wüster, Eugen. 1968. The Machine Tool: An Interlingual Dictionary of Basic Concepts. London: Technical Press.
8. Зорин И.В., Каверина Т.П., Квартальнов В.А. и др. Менеджмент туризма. Туризм как вид деятельности: Учебник. М.: Финансы и статистика, 2006. С. 406
9. Макаренко С.Н., Саак А.Э. История туризма. — Таганрог: Издательство ТРТУ, 2003. С. 94

